

Analysis of Digital Ads, Online Selling, Online Customer Experience, on Purchase Intention using Brand Awareness Variable as Mediation Variable in 2021-2022 Pandemic (Case Study on Legoproject.id)

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Abstract:- This study explains the influence of Digital Ads, Online Selling, Online Customer Experience, on Purchase Intention Using Brand Awareness Variables as Mediation Variables during the 2021-2022 Pandemic by using case studies on Legoproject.Id. The research method used is quantitative research using a structured questionnaire. The determination of the number of samples used in this study was based on the Hair formula with the number of samples to be used in the study being 185 people who had transacted at legoproject.id. This study uses five variables, namely digital advertising, online selling, Online Customer Experience, Purchase Intention, Brand awareness. The data in this study were obtained from primary sources using a questionnaire distributed to consumers of Lego project.id which was then measured using a Likert Scale. Testing the research hypothesis was carried out using the Partial Least Square (PLS) approach based on the Structural Equation Model (SEM). The results of this study are that digital advertising and customer experience are important factors and can directly influence customer purchase intentions, while online sales are not a significant factor that can influence customer purchase intentions. Brand awareness is a factor capable of influencing purchase intention, and also plays a mediating role in the relationship between digital advertising, online sales, consumer experience, and purchase intention. Theoretical implications of this study are that it is anticipated to be able to conduct both studies, namely qualitative and quantitative to provide more in-depth research results and more effective suggestions, using variables that are not used in the pre-survey table, and further research can be conducted on other business sectors or in e-commerce because it is possible to produce different conclusions with different objects. The practical implications of this research, must pay attention to marketing factors that affect brand awareness such as digital advertising and customer experience during transactions that can affect customer purchase intentions, where most customers will be more interested in buying things that are more familiar to them.

Keywords:- Brand Awareness; Digital Ads; Online Selling; Online Customer Experience, Purchase Intention

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the countries affected by the Covid-19 outbreak since early March 2020 is Indonesia, which has had a significant negative impact on all areas of life, especially the economic sector. The inability to leave the house limits the space for people to move. The practice of working from home (WFH) has influenced the development of online flower trading. All age groups are getting in on the trend of buying flowers online because there are demands to be met, not just young customers. The trend of buying interest online is not only carried out by young consumers but also by all age groups because there are needs that must be met. Seeing the situation and the intense competition for businesses to survive during the pandemic, it can be seen that several brands are doing marketing using digital ads to increase sales and get profits in business. One of the businesses on Instagram that has been on the rise during the pandemic is Legoproject.id, where they sell related accessories made from LEGO. Digital ads, online sales, and online customer experience are one of Legoproject.id's strategies in increasing its brand awareness. Advertising can influence a customer's decision to purchase a product or service for the first time. Depending on the customer's pleasure with the product and its advantages, this decision may lead to continuing or intermittent usage of the product. Based on the above, the purpose of this research is to analyze Digital Ads, Online Selling, Online Customer Experience, Against Purchase Intention Using Brand Awareness Variables as Mediation Variables During the 2021-2022 Pandemic Period using Case Studies on Legoproject.Id.

II. HYPOTHESIS

A. Relationship between Digital Advertising and Brand Awareness

Kasali's research (2002) says that brand awareness, because in a strategy to increase consumer awareness, producers must create attractive advertisements for their target audience. These results are in line with research conducted by Eriko (2012) which shows that advertising has a positive influence in building brand awareness of a product.

H1: Digital Advertising has a positive and significant effect on brand awareness

B. Relationship between Online Selling and Brand Awareness

One way to retain consumers is to build brand awareness. Every company must try to make their brand the best brand to further strengthen and expand their business.

H2: Online selling has a positive and significant influence on brand awareness

C. Relationship between Online Customer Experience and Brand Awareness

Consumers who are happy with a brand will form a familiar impression on it, according to Cherng G. Ding et al. (2015) pointed out the beneficial role that customer experience plays in increasing brand recognition among consumers. The findings of this study indicate that brand awareness is positively and significantly influenced by online customer experience variables.

H3: Customer Experience has a positive and significant effect on Brand Awareness

D. Relationship between Digital Advertising and Purchase Intention

Advertising can influence a customer's decision to purchase a product or service for the first time. Depending on the customer's pleasure with the product and its advantages, this decision may lead to continuing or intermittent usage of the product.

H4: Digital advertising has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention

E. Relationship between Online Selling and Purchase Intention

Rossiter and Percy in Nababan (2008:20) stated that the convenience and comfort offered by brands with online sales for customers will increase interest in the brand without having to waste the customer's time so that the possibility of someone making a purchase will be even higher.

H5: Online selling has a positive and significant influence on purchase intention

F. Relationship between Online Customer Experience and Purchase Intention

According to Shilpa Bagdare and Rajnish Jain (2013) stated that the influence of customer experience on shopping at retail. The results of this study indicate that there is a positive influence on consumer experience in shopping at retail on the product buying process.

H6: Online Customer Experience has a positive and significant effect on Purchase Intention.

G. Relationship between Brand Awareness and Purchase Intention

Research conducted by Yudhiartika & Haryanto (2012) states that sales promotion has a significant positive effect on brand awareness of POND'S beauty products. In this study it can be seen that sales promotion describes incentives and gifts to make customers buy company goods now rather than later. This unique and creative promotion can create brand awareness of the product.

H7: Brand Awareness has a positive and significant influence on Purchase Intention

H. Relationship between digital advertising and purchase intent via brand awareness medium.

Using a jar analysis model, Sienatra (2020) conducts research to examine the relationship between advertising and brand awareness. The results of this study show that advertising has a significant impact on brand recognition, and brand recognition has a significant impact on the perception of product value.

H8: Digital advertising improves purchase intention through brand awareness medium.

I. Relationship between internet sales and consumer intent via brand recognition

When a product or brand has strong brand recognition among consumers, this will influence their buying intent or behavior. This is because consumers will be more likely to purchase the products they are familiar with (Keller, 1993; Macdonald & Sharp, 2000).

H9: Online selling improves purchase intent through brand awareness media.

J. Link between online customer experience and purchase intent through media brand awareness

The results of Maziyya and Martini's research from 2021 show that think experience has a favorable effect on repurchase intent. This is due to people being unsatisfied with the advice given, such as campaigns or special offers that businesses have already made for their customers.

H10: Online customer experience has an impact on purchase intent through medias that raise brand awareness.

III. METHODS

The research method used is quantitative research using a structured questionnaire. The determination of the number of samples used in this study was based on the Hair formula with the number of samples to be used in the study being 185 people who had transacted at legoproject.id. This study uses five variables, namely digital advertising, online selling, Online Customer Experience, Purchase Intention, Brand awareness. The data in this study were obtained from primary sources using a questionnaire distributed to consumers of Lego project.id which was then measured using a Likert Scale. Testing the research hypothesis was carried out using the Partial Least Square (PLS) based Structural Equation Model (SEM) approach.

IV. DISCUSSIONS

Primary data in this study resulted from direct data collection from respondents through questionnaires distributed to Legoproject.id consumers as many as 185 respondents.

A. Convergent Validity Test

Convergent validity values are used to determine the validity of a construct. An indication of the loading factor value exceeding the study limit set at 0.5 is considered valid. The results of the validity test are shown in table 1 below:

Variabel	Item	Nilai Outer Loading	Batasan Nilai Outer Loading	Keputusan
Digital Advertising (X1)	Item1	0,893	0,7	Valid
	Item2	0,883	0,7	Valid
	Item3	0,893	0,7	Valid
	Item4	0,868	0,7	Valid
	Item5	0,793	0,7	Valid
	Item6	0,863	0,7	Valid
Online selling (X2)	Item1	0,853	0,7	Valid
	Item2	0,881	0,7	Valid
	Item3	0,869	0,7	Valid
	Item4	0,854	0,7	Valid
	Item5	0,871	0,7	Valid
	Item6	0,761	0,7	Valid
	Item7	0,751	0,7	Valid
Customer Experience (X3)	Item1	0,872	0,7	Valid
	Item2	0,864	0,7	Valid
	Item3	0,890	0,7	Valid
	Item4	0,864	0,7	Valid
	Item5	0,851	0,7	Valid
	Item6	0,823	0,7	Valid
	Item7	0,880	0,7	Valid
	Item8	0,878	0,7	Valid
	Item9	0,875	0,7	Valid
	Item10	0,846	0,7	Valid
	Item11	0,890	0,7	Valid
	Item12	0,866	0,7	Valid
	Item13	0,794	0,7	Valid
	Item14	0,763	0,7	Valid
	Item15	0,878	0,7	Valid
Brand Awareness (Y1)	Item1	0,903	0,7	Valid
	Item2	0,885	0,7	Valid
	Item3	0,913	0,7	Valid
	Item4	0,894	0,7	Valid
Purchase Intention (Y2)	Item1	0,893	0,7	Valid
	Item2	0,921	0,7	Valid
	Item3	0,902	0,7	Valid
	Item4	0,907	0,7	Valid
	Item5	0,812	0,7	Valid

Table 1: Validity Test Results (Convergent Validity)

From table 1 above it can be seen that all items with loading factor values (outer loading) are all above 0.7 and declared valid.

B. Reliability Test (Composite Reliability and Cronbach Alpha) and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) Test

The following is the data from the analysis results from the Cronbach's alpha test, Composite reliability, and the AVE value:

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Limit Reliability	Decision
Digital Advertising (X1)	0,883	0,947	0,700	Reliabel
Online selling (X2)	0,928	0,942	0,700	Reliabel
Customer Experience	0,974	0,976	0,700	Reliabel
(X3)Brand Awareness	0,921	0,944	0,700	Reliabel
(Y1)	0,933	0,949	0,700	Reliabel
Purchase Intention (Y2)				

Table 2: Reliability Test (Composite Reliability and Cronbach Alpha) and Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Source: Data processed with SmartPLS, 2023

The composite reliability of the test and Cronbach's alpha score, which is based on results 2 and the table above, is quite strong, with a value of each variable above 0.70. This shows that this instrument is very stable. In other

words, all study variables or constructs have developed into reliable measurement tools, and all questions used to evaluate each construct have a high level of validity.

C. Average Variance Extracted Test (AVE)

Variable	AVE Value	AVE Value Limitation	Decision
Digital Advertising (X1)	0,750	0,500	Fulfilled
Online selling (X2)	0,699	0,500	Fulfilled
Customer Experience (X3)	0,733	0,500	Fulfilled
Brand Awareness (Y1)	0,808	0,500	Fulfilled
Purchase Intention (Y2)	0,789	0,500	Fulfilled

Table 3: Average Variance Extracted Test (AVE)

Source: Data processed with SmartPLS, 2023

D. Discriminant Validity Test

	Digital Advertising (X1)	Online Selling (X2)	Online Customer Experience (X3)	Brand Awareness (Z)	Purchase Intention (Y)
X1.01	0.893	0.542	0.534	0.578	0.575
X1.02	0.883	0.487	0.475	0.573	0.558
X1.03	0.893	0.492	0.518	0.578	0.556
X1.04	0.868	0.590	0.504	0.577	0.572
X1.05	0.793	0.430	0.443	0.479	0.530
X1.06	0.863	0.526	0.468	0.567	0.533
X2.01	0.525	0.853	0.257	0.348	0.374
X2.02	0.547	0.881	0.276	0.355	0.352
X2.03	0.537	0.869	0.298	0.375	0.307
X2.04	0.534	0.854	0.256	0.371	0.347
X2.05	0.514	0.871	0.316	0.378	0.378
X2.06	0.366	0.761	0.244	0.307	0.229
X2.07	0.400	0.751	0.173	0.280	0.231
X3.01	0.535	0.322	0.872	0.468	0.504
X3.02	0.525	0.242	0.864	0.501	0.484
X3.03	0.484	0.299	0.890	0.505	0.453
X3.04	0.501	0.265	0.864	0.536	0.456
X3.05	0.436	0.267	0.851	0.506	0.422
X3.06	0.503	0.244	0.823	0.480	0.434
X3.07	0.528	0.294	0.880	0.574	0.479
X3.08	0.517	0.259	0.878	0.573	0.500
X3.09	0.489	0.281	0.875	0.513	0.462
X3.10	0.486	0.265	0.846	0.477	0.477
X3.11	0.467	0.243	0.890	0.437	0.419
X3.12	0.496	0.340	0.866	0.538	0.443
X3.13	0.440	0.241	0.794	0.440	0.362
X3.14	0.385	0.192	0.763	0.377	0.380
X3.15	0.460	0.266	0.878	0.450	0.470
Y1.01	0.582	0.39	0.541	0.903	0.531
Y1.02	0.551	0.418	0.508	0.885	0.490
Y1.03	0.581	0.329	0.534	0.913	0.574

Table 4: Discriminant Validity Test

	Digital Advertising (X1)	Online Selling (X2)	Online Customer Experience (X3)	Brand Awareness (Z)	Purchase Intention (Y)
X1 (DA)	0.866				
X2 (OS)	0.592	0.836			
X3 (OCE)	0.567	0.315	0.856		
Z (BA)	0.646	0.415	0.578	0.899	
Y (PI)	0.64	0.386	0.528	0.594	0.888

Table 5: AVE Root Value Results and Correlation Between Constructs

Source: Data processed with SmartPLS, 2023

From the output of Table 4, namely Discriminant validity Cross Loading, all indicators have a greater correlation coefficient with each of its own variables compared to the correlation coefficient values of the indicators with other variables, so it is concluded that each indicator in the block is a constructor of variables or

constructs. in that column. In table 5 it can be seen that the AVE root value of each variable is higher than the correlation value between that variable and the other variables in the model. With this, it can be said that according to the test with the AVE roots, this model has good discriminant validity.

E. Inner Model Test

➤ R Square analysis

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Y1 (BA)	0.486	0.477
Y2 (PI)	0.482	0.470

Sumber: Data diolah dengan SmartPLS, 2023

Table 6: R Square Value Results

The findings show that brand awareness has an impact on Legoproject.id's purchase intention in 2022. Ho is rejected and Ha is approved because the T Statistical value of 3.050 is greater than 1.96 or the P value of 0.002 is less than 0.05. The seventh hypothesis, "Brand Awareness has a beneficial influence on purchase intentions of Lego project.id in 2022," is supported by data and can be

accepted. According to Febriani and Dewi (2018), brand awareness refers to the brand's ability to stick in people's memories, reflected in their minds, and allows people to recognize various brand elements (such as brand names, logos, symbols, characters, packaging, and slogans) in various context.

➤ Effect size (f2)

	Digital Advertising (X1)	Online Selling (X2)	Online Customer Experience (X3)	Brand Awareness (Y1)	Purchase Intention (Y2)
X1 (DA)				0.178	0.117
X2 (OS)				0.005	0.000
X3 (OCE)				0.130	0.032
Y1 (BA)					0.062
Y2 (PI)					

Sumber: Data diolah dengan SmartPLS, 2023

Table 7: Results of the value of f Square

The result of the value of f2 produces a value of 0.02, then the influence of exogenous latent variables is small, a value of 0.15 means that the effect of exogenous latent variables is declared medium, and a value of 0.35 means that the influence of exogenous latent variables is declared large. Based on the following table namely

- The variable X1 to Y1 has an f square value of 0.178, the effect is moderate.
- The variable X1 to Y2 has an f square value of 0.117, the effect is moderate.

- The variable X2 to Y1 has an f square value of 0.005, the effect is relatively small.
- The variable X2 to Y2 has an f square value of 0.000, the effect is relatively small
- The variable X3 to Y1 has an f square value of 0.130, the effect is classified as sedan
- The variable X3 to Y2 has an f square value of 0.032, the effect is relatively small.

- The variable Y1 to Y2 has an f square value of 0.062, the effect is relatively small.

F. Predictive Relevance (Q2)

If $Q2 > 0$ indicates the model has predictive relevance and if the value of $Q2 < 0$ indicates that the model lacks predictive relevance (Ghozali and Latan, 2015: 81).

Construct Crossvalidated Redundancy

	SSO	SSE	Q2(=1-SSE/SSO)
X1 (DA)	1110.000	1110.000	
X2 (OS)	1295.000	1295.000	
X3 (OCE)	2775.000	2775.000	
Y1 (BA)	740.000	453.508	0.387
Y2 (PI)	925.000	579.505	0.374

Table 8: Q2 Value Results

Source: Data processed with SmartPLS, 2023

From the output above, it can be seen that the Q2 values are 0.387 and 0.374. Because the value is greater than 0, the model has predictive relevance.

G. Goodness of Fit Index (GoF)

The criterion value is 0.10 (GoF small), value is 0.25 (GoF medium), and value is 0.36 (GoF large) (Ghozali and Latan, 2015: 83). The GoF test is calculated using Ms Excel. The result is 0.605. So GoF is big.

➤ **Model Fit Test**

Model Fit

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.041	0.041
d_ULS	1.194	1.194
d_G	0.888	0.888
Chi-Square	873.661	873.661
NFI	0.876	0.876

Table 9: Model Fit Test Results

Source: Data processed with SmartPLS, 2023

From the output above it can be seen that the SRMR value is 0.041 so that the model is appropriate or meets the goodness of fit model criteria.

Testing the proposed hypothesis is done by looking at the path coefficients which show the parameter coefficients and the statistical significance value of t. The limit for rejecting and accepting the proposed hypothesis is using a probability of 0.05.

➤ **Hypothesis Testing (Effect between variables)**

Specific Indirect Effect

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics ((O/STDEV))	P Values
X1 (DA) > Y1 (BA) > Y2 (PI)	0.108	0.113	0.048	2.232	0.026
X2 (OS) > Y1 (BA) > Y2 (PI)	0.015	0.018	0.017	0.878	0.380
X3 (OCE) > Y1 (BA) > Y2 (PI)	0.079	0.080	0.031	2.527	0.012

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics ((O/STDEV))	P Values
X1 (DA) > Y1 (BA)	0.432	0.432	0.087	4.982	0.000
X1 (DA) > Y2 (PI)	0.382	0.382	0.085	4.469	0.000
X2 (OS) > Y1 (BA)	0.061	0.066	0.058	1.061	0.289
X2 (OS) > Y2 (PI)	0.004	0.001	0.069	0.062	0.951
X3 (OCE) > Y1 (BA)	0.314	0.314	0.083	3.799	0.000
X3 (OCE) > Y2 (PI)	0.165	0.166	0.078	2.110	0.035
Y1 (BA) > Y2 (PI)	0.250	0.258	0.082	3.050	0.002

Table 10: Hypothesis Test Results

H. Digital Advertising Variable Analysis of Brand Awareness (Hypothesis 1)

The research results show that Digital Advertising has an effect on Legoproject.id brand awareness in 2022. This is because the T Statistics value is 4.982 greater than 1.96 or the P values are 0.000 less than 0.05, so H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. A positive coefficient value means that Digital Advertising has a positive effect on Legoproject.id brand awareness in 2022, that is, if Digital Advertising increases, brand awareness also increases, or if Digital Advertising decreases, brand awareness also decreases. The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Aurinawati and Fitriani entitled *The Influence of Digital Marketing on Increasing Brand Awareness and Brand Image on Purchase Decisions for Chocolate Monggo Products in Yogyakarta in 2020* which states that digital marketing (both through social media and online marketing media) others) on increasing brand awareness and brand image on product purchasing decisions.

I. Analysis of Online Selling Variables on Brand Awareness (Hypothesis 2)

The second hypothesis which states "Online selling has a positive effect on Legoproject.id brand awareness in 2022" is not proven and can be declared not accepted. The T Statistics value of 1.061 is less than 1.96 or the P value is 0.289 more than 0.05, so H_0 is accepted and H_a is rejected. Adi and Prasetya (2015) which state that consumer behavior is increasingly leading to an online lifestyle, one of which is the increasingly inseparable consumers from smartphone or gadget devices, nowadays it is not a factor that has a direct influence on increasing consumers, but only a supporting factor that makes it easier introduction and education about online shopping

J. Analysis of Customer Experience Variables on Brand Awareness (Hypothesis 3)

The research results show that Customer Experience has an effect on Legoproject.id brand awareness in 2022. This is because the T Statistics value is 3.799 greater than 1.96 or the P value is 0.000 less than 0.05, so H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. The third hypothesis which states "Customer Experience has a positive effect on Legoproject.id brand awareness in 2022" is proven and can be declared accepted. The results of this study are in line with the results of research conducted by Reza (2021) that in order to increase guest interest in returning, the customer experience can stimulate customer motivation, thus increasing the value of products and services. A positive customer experience can encourage the creation of an emotional bond between the company's brand and customers which in turn will increase the interest to visit again because they are satisfied with the company.

K. Variable Analysis of the Effect of Digital Advertising on Purchase Intention (Hypothesis 4)

The findings of this study are consistent with research by Reza (2021), who found that a positive customer experience can increase consumer motivation and increase the perceived value of goods and services by increasing customer interest to return. A satisfying customer experience can promote the development of an emotional

connection between a company's brand and its audience, which in turn will increase consumer desire to return.

L. Variable Analysis of the Influence of Online Selling on Purchase Intention (Hypothesis 5)

The research findings show that the intention to buy Legoproject.id in 2022 is not affected by online retail. H_0 was approved while H_a was rejected because the T Statistic value was 0.062 which was less than 1.96, or the P value was 0.951 which was more than 0.05. The final claim, "Internet sales have a favorable effect on purchase intention Legoproject.id in 2022," has not been supported and thus rejected. In this case, the authors argue that customer decisions to buy products sold online are influenced by interactions between online sales.

M. Variable Analysis of the Effect of Customer Experience on Purchase Intention (Hypothesis 6)

The study findings show that customers' shopping experience will have an impact on their purchase intention in 2022 when they visit Legoproject.id. Because the T Statistics value of 2.110 is higher than 1.96 or the P value is 0.035 lower than 0.05, then H_0 is rejected while H_a is approved. The sixth theory which states that "Digital Advertising has a positive impact on the purchase intention of Legoproject.id in 2022" is proven valid and can be defended. The results of this study are in line with Penny Rahmawati's research which found that customer experience with companies is a subjective and internal response to these interactions.

N. Variable Analysis of the Effect of Brand Awareness on Purchase Intention (Hypothesis 7)

The findings show that brand awareness has an impact on Legoproject.id's purchase intention in 2022. H_0 is rejected and H_a is approved because the T Statistical value of 3.050 is greater than 1.96 or the P value of 0.002 is less than 0.05. The seventh hypothesis, "Brand Awareness has a beneficial influence on purchase intentions of Legoproject.id in 2022," is supported by data and can be accepted. According to Febriani and Dewi (2018), brand awareness refers to the brand's ability to stick in people's memories, reflected in their minds, and allows people to recognize various brand elements (such as brand names, logos, symbols, characters, packaging, and slogans) in various context.

O. Analyzing the Influence of Digital Advertising on Buy Intention through Brand Awareness (Hypothesis 8)

The results of this study demonstrate that internet advertising influences purchase intent via brand recognition. H_0 is therefore rejected while H_a is accepted because the P value of 0.026 is less than 0.05 and the T statistic value of 2.232 is more than 1.96. According to the data supporting it, the eighth hypothesis, "Digital advertising has an influence on purchase intention through the mediation of brand awareness," can be accepted. This is consistent with Sienatra's research (2020), which claims that brand recognition and product purchase decisions are both significantly influenced by advertising.

P. An examination of how brand awareness influences purchase intention while shopping online (Hypothesis 9)

According to the results of the study, the variable of online selling had no effect on purchase intent via brand awareness mediation. H_0 is approved while H_a is refused because the T statistic value of 0.878 is less than 1.96 or the P value is 0.380 higher than 0.05. Hence, the ninth hypothesis—that "online selling has an influence on purchase intention through the mediation of brand awareness"—is deemed unreliable and unsatisfactory. This contradicts earlier research by Wayne D. Hoyer and Steven P. Brown (1990), which found that consumers' purchase intentions are affected by a product or brand's level of brand awareness because they prefer or are more likely to purchase things they are familiar with (Keller, 1993; Macdonald & Sharp, 2000).

Q. An examination of how brand awareness mediates the impact of online customer experience on purchase intention (Hypothesis 10)

In this study, it was discovered that online customer experience influenced purchase intent via brand recognition. H_0 is therefore rejected while H_a is accepted because the P value of 0.012 is less than 0.05 and the T statistic value of 2.527 is greater than 1.96. Given this, it can be concluded that the eleventh hypothesis, which claims that "Only Customer Experience has an influence on Buy Intention through the mediation of Brand Awareness," is true. This is consistent with studies by Pasharibu et al. (2018) that found favorable effects of sense experience, feel experience, act experience, and relate experience on purchase intention. In the meanwhile, I don't believe experience influences purchasing intention favorably.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The results of the analysis in this study show that digital advertising and customer experience are important factors and can directly influence customer purchase intentions, while online sales are not a significant factor that can influence customer purchase intentions. Brand awareness is a factor capable of influencing purchase intention, and it also plays a mediating role in the relationship between digital advertising, online sales, consumer experience and purchase intention.

VI. LIMITATION AND IMPLICATION

Based on the data analysis and research results described above, the implications of this research are theoretical and practical implications. Theoretically, the results of this research are follow-up research related to variables that have negative results in this study as a renewal and development of marketing theory in the future. The practical implications of this research must pay attention to marketing factors that influence brand awareness such as digital advertising and customer experience during transactions that can affect customer purchase intentions, where most customers will be more interested in buying things that are more familiar to them. In addition, brands

and business people do not need to focus on the online sales factor because it is not a significant factor, in addition to the brand or business to continuously evaluate the level of customer awareness regarding brand awareness that is being marketed as well as the level of customer satisfaction to measure marketing efficiency for products that are marketed. marketed and determine effective marketing strategies to drive customer purchase intentions.

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